

5-bromosalicylaldehyde (5-BSAO) were prepared by refluxing the respective aldehyde with hydroxylamine hydrochloride³. The products obtained were recrystallised from ethanol. A standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solution⁴ (0.98 M) was used as the titrant.

The dissociation constants of the ligands and their formation constants with Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} were determined in the water-ethanol (50%, v/v) medium at ionic strength 0.1 M and temperature 25° by potentiometric titrations as described earlier⁵. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH SAO AND ITS SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES

Ethanol-Water = 50% (v/v), Ionic strength = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), Temp. = 25°

Cation	Constant	SAO	3-MSAO	5-MSAO	5-BSAO
H ⁺	log K_{OH}^H	10.60	10.82	11.15	9.89
	log K_{NOH}^H	12.73	12.69	12.75	12.65
Co ^{II}	log K_1	6.90	7.02	7.41	6.70
Mn ^{II}	log K_1	6.09	6.02	6.77	5.89
Zn ^{II}	log K_1	5.67	5.71	6.28	5.68

Results and Discussion

In all cases the stability constant values follow the order, Co > Mn > Zn. A comparison of the stability constant values of salicylaldehyde and its substituted derivatives with the corresponding values for complexes of the substituted-salicylaldehydes⁵ reveals that log K_1 values for ligands of (NO⁻) type are always higher than that for the ligands of (OO⁻) type.

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Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-III. Solution Equilibria in the Complex Formation of Bivalent Metal Ions with Thiosemicarbazones of *vic*-Hydroxy aldehydes

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THE pharmacology of thiosemicarbazones and their complexes has expanded dramatically since its initiation¹ in 1946 in the study of antitubercular activity. There has been considerable research in the field of physiological activity of the ligands and their ability to form chelates with metals. But no significant investigation has been made about the properties of the complexes in solution. The present paper deals with the formation constants of the complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (SATSC), 3-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (3-MSATSC), 4-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (4-MSATSC), 5-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-MSATSC) and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-BSATSC) using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) at 25° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

X = H, 3-CH₃, 4-OH, 5-OH, 5-Br.

Experimental

The thiosemicarbazones of salicylaldehyde were prepared by refluxing 3-CH₃-salicylaldehyde, 4-CH₃-salicylaldehyde, 5-CH₃-salicylaldehyde and 5-Br-salicylaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide. For synthesis of thiosemicarbazones general procedure² of condensation was used with certain modifications. The products obtained were recrystallised from ethanol. Carbonate-free NaOH (AnalaR) solution³ (0.98 M) was standardised with succinic acid. A 4 M sodium perchlorate (E. Merck, G.R.) solution was used for adjusting the ionic strength. A 70% perchloric acid (E. Merck, A.R.) solution was diluted with distilled water to obtain 2.0 and 0.2 M solutions. Solutions of the ligands (0.04 M) were prepared in ethanol. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared by treating 20 ml of 2 M HClO₄

with excess of the respective oxide or carbonate (A.R.) and suitably diluting the resulting neutral solution to 0.2 M. The metal contents were determined by standard procedures⁴.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out as described earlier⁵. The pH meter reading in 50% ethanol were corrected for solvent effect⁶. The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere of oxygen-free nitrogen pre-saturated with the solvent medium. Nitrogen served the purpose of stirring the titration solution also.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants and the metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by using half-integral, graphical and least-square methods (Table 1). In case of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} only 1 : 1 complexes have been studied since at higher pH value 1 : 2 complexes precipitate. In case of Cu^{II}, both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes could be studied since there is no precipitation even at higher pH.

Esr, electronic and far-ir spectra confirm strong metal-sulphur bond in these compounds.

In case of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazones and related compounds, there is an additional phenolic OH group and *vic*-hydroxy aldehyde thiosemicarbazones undergo first deprotonation in the phenolic OH whereas the second deprotonation in the thiol group. Mono-deprotonated and di-deprotonated species are formed successively in the first and second processes of ionisations. Ligands are, therefore, likely to be tridentate with oxygen, sulphur and nitrogen as the active atoms.

The ionisation constants of the ligands show linear relationship with Hammett σ values and obey the relation,

$$pK_1^H = 9.93 - \rho \Sigma \sigma \\ = 9.93 - 3.5 \Sigma \sigma$$

The second ionisation of the thiol proton however shows a constant value and there is hardly any effect of the substituent on the ionisation constant.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND SYSTEMS OF SATSC AND ITS SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES

Cation	Constant*	Temp. = 25°, Ethanol-water = 50%, $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO ₄)				
		SATSC	3-MSATSC	4-MSATSC	5-MSATSC	5-BSATSC
H ⁺	log K_{OH}^H	^a 9.93	10.15	10.28	10.63	9.13
	log K_{SH}^H	^b 9.93	10.13	10.30	10.59	9.04
Cu ^{II}	log K_1	^a 12.43	12.85	12.43	12.73	12.30
		^b 12.47	12.80	12.37	12.72	12.29
		^a 9.43	9.37	9.62	10.01	8.60
		^b 9.42	9.38	9.63	10.03	8.60
log K_2		^c 9.45	9.23	9.54	10.12	8.58
		^a 8.70	8.48	9.00	9.47	8.04
		^b 8.73	8.48	8.98	9.47	8.05
Co ^{II}	log K_1	^c 8.95	8.51	8.95	9.66	8.13
		^a 9.12	8.59	8.77	9.48	7.69
Ni ^{II}	log K_1	^b 9.02	8.59	8.68	9.49	7.69
		^a 8.72	8.32	8.39	8.96	6.90
Mn ^{II}	log K_1	^b 8.77	8.32	8.41	8.97	6.90
		^a 6.48	7.51	6.53	6.93	6.15
Zn ^{II}	log K_1	^b 6.48	7.55	6.53	6.98	6.19
		^a 6.21	7.32	6.32	6.70	5.93
Cd ^{II}	log K_1	^b 6.16	7.33	6.32	6.61	5.95
		^a 5.22	5.99	5.41	5.59	5.15
		^b 5.18	6.00	5.46	5.57	5.15

*Method : ^aHalf-integral, ^bGraphical, ^cLeast-square.

The study of complexes of thiosemicarbazones reveals that the bonding to metal ions is through sulphur atom of thiol group and coordination through hydrazinic nitrogen atoms⁷. In a few cases they behave as monodentate ligands where bonding is through thiol sulphur. It is quite clear that the most important single factor affecting the behaviour of thiosemicarbazone ligands is the nature of sulphur donor atom. The scanty thermodynamic data available from solid state study explain that the stability constants of complexes with soft or class (b) metal ions is due to a large enthalpy term which signifies strong metal-sulphur bond⁸.

Order of log K_1 values for metal complexes: There are reports on the general trend of the stability constants by Calvin-Bjerrum techniques⁹⁻¹². The order of stability constants in the above reports is as follows: Cu > Co > Ni¹³, Cu $\approx$ Co > Ni¹⁴, Cu > Co > Ni¹⁵, Cu > Co > Ni > Mn > Zn > Cd > Mg¹⁶, and in the present work, Cu > Co > Ni > Mn > Zn > Cd; Irving-Williams rule¹⁸ is not strictly obeyed and Co and Ni show reverse order.

Infrared spectra of ligands: Ir spectral data for SATSC was reported by Gingras *et al.*¹⁴ who

attributed the bands at 3 460, 3 330 and 3 180 cm^{-1} to secondary $-\text{NHCSNH}_2$ group. The spectra of the thiosemicarbazones of substituted salicylaldehydes show similar bands. The SH stretch in mercaptans and thiophenols absorbs¹⁵ at 2 590–2 540 cm^{-1} . Due to the greater mass of sulphur the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ is expected to occur at considerably lower frequencies than the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibration in the C–O or C–N region. This means that the C=S and the attached single bonds can interact with the result that more than one band involves C=S stretch¹⁶. Gingras *et al.*¹⁷ attributed the band at 1 130–1 080 cm^{-1} in the spectra of several thiosemicarbazones to the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ because the band in this region disappears on complex formation. A simple calculation of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ by using Gordy's rule and harmonic oscillation equation gave a value of 6×10^5 dyne cm^{-1} for the stretching force constant, corresponding to 1 080 cm^{-1} . A more accurate calculation predicts C=S stretching modes¹⁶ at 1 450, 1 059 and 757 cm^{-1} . The absorption in the region 830–805 cm^{-1} in spectra of thiosemicarbazones should be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$. The 1 532 cm^{-1} band is assigned¹⁸ as mainly $\nu_{\text{CN}+\delta\text{NH}_2}$.

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Potentiometric Studies on some Ternary Complexes of Neodymium(III)

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IN continuation of our previous work on complexation equilibria of lanthanides^{1,2}, the present paper reports the binary complexation behaviour of Nd^{III} with suberic acid $[\text{HOOC}(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{COOH}]$ (SA) and azelaic acid $[\text{HOOC}(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{COOH}]$ (AA) and ternary $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}-\text{HEDTA}-(\text{SA or AA})$ equilibria at 25° and $\mu=0.1 M \text{KNO}_3$. The ternary equilibria were also studied at two other temperatures 5 and 45° at $\mu=0.1 M \text{KNO}_3$. The effects of change in dielectric constant and ionic strength have also been studied.

Experimental

Solutions of HEDTA (Sigma), SA (Fluka, A.G.) and AA (Fluka, A.G.) were prepared in oxygen-free double-distilled water and were standardised potentiometrically by titrating with sodium hydroxide solution³. All other reagents were of A.R. grade. Nd^{III} solution was standardised by EDTA method⁴.

Procedure for the pH-metric study of binary systems was the same as described earlier⁵ maintaining a metal–ligand ratio of 1:5 except that instead of perchloric acid, nitric acid was used in the present case. For mixed ligand systems the procedure was the same as described earlier⁶. To

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